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**ІНДИВІДУАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ЛЮДЕЙ З
РІЗНИМИ ТИПАМИ ПРИХИЛЬНОСТІ
INDIVIDUAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
PEOPLE WITH DIFFERENT TYPES OF ATTACHMENT**

Кожного дня особистість стикається з різними людьми та має з ними контактувати. Успішність соціальної взаємодії найчастіше залежить від умінь особистості використовувати свої особливості. Особливості роботи емоційної сфери мають певний вплив на успішність спілкування. Коли індивідуальність вміє урегулювати, демонструвати та розуміти свої емоційні стани та інших – її можна назвати емоційно зрілою.

Особливості праці психічних функцій закладені не тільки на біологічному рівні, але ще і значний вплив на їх роботу має середовище, в якому виховується людина. Перший об'єкт з яким стикається людина – це її мати, яка забезпечує індивіду середовище, в якому та буде розвиватися. Кожна мати має певний стиль виховання та свої особливості поведінки, в залежності від них формується тип прихильності, які впливають на характер сприйняття стосунків з оточуючими та світом майбутньої особистості. Саме тип прихильності формує особливості сприйняття, емоцій та поведінки людини.

Дослідження, яке було проведено нами було спрямовано на з'ясування особливостей взаємозв'язків емоційної зрілості з різними типами прихильності. У дослідженні ми спиралися на особливості емоційної сфери особистостей в залежності від їх типу прив'язаності та їх сприйняття певних ситуацій в яких може опинитися кожна людина.

Ключові слова: емоційна зрілість, прихильність, надійна прихильність, амбівалентна прихильність, уникаюча прихильність, неорганізаційна прихильність.

Keywords: emotional maturity, attachment, secure attachment, ambivalent attachment, avoidant attachment, non-organizational attachment.

Emotional maturity is the ability of an individual to skillfully manipulate internal states, establish them, understand them, and transmit them to the outside as harmoniously and efficiently as possible.

The main components of emotional maturity are:

- Regulation of emotions;
- Expression in the expression of emotions;
- Empathy. The ability of an individual to understand his emotions and reflect them in the surrounding environment.

Emotional connections with a loved one are the basis of attachment. The

quality of attachment affects a person's emotional state and his regulatory abilities. The type of attachment is formed in childhood. Affection is an exchange of comfort, emotional warmth, and pleasure. The founder of the theory, J. Bowie, was a representative of the psychoanalytic approach and held the position that childhood experiences directly affect the formation of a personality in adulthood and its social relationships. According to him, attachment is a stable psychological connection between individuals, the type of which is formed in early childhood. Scientist E. Ainsworth continued J. Bowie's research and identified the following types of attachment:

- **Reliable attachment.** The personality is not afraid to express various emotions openly, it can freely talk about them and emphasize what it feels at this very moment. A person who is securely attached to the object of affection feels free to be overwhelmed by emotions.

- **Avoidant attachment.** Such an individual cannot demonstrate his emotions openly, as he feels the fear of being turned away. Avoiding individuals suppress their emotions and try not to show a desire to be in a relationship. Most often, people with an avoidant type feel discomfort from positive emotions, such as joy and happiness. In their opinion, these emotions are not effective.

- **Ambivalent attachment.** An ambivalent personality hyperbolizes his emotions to attract the attention of others. Most often, negative emotions are an exaggeration. A person with this type of attachment can be more attractive to others than a person with a secure attachment, due to the self-disclosure of the inner world.

Later, scientists M. Main and J. Solomon singled out another type of attachment – disorganized. Such a person has a low level of emotional intelligence, has difficulties in understanding his emotions and the emotions of others. They will show features of rigid behavior, not tolerant of uncertainty. Most often, they cannot express their position and do so thanks to other people's opinions. They really long for deep and healthy romantic kisses, but they don't know how to build them.

In order to empirically and practically work out the problem of individual psychological characteristics of emotional maturity in persons with different types of attachment, a psychological study was planned and conducted using an Internet survey, which was conducted in Google forms. 50 people aged 18 to 30 took part in the study. Correlation analysis was performed using SPSS for Windows version 16.0.

The purpose of the study: to reveal the individual and psychological characteristics of people with different types of attachment.

For the study, the following was used: "Questionnaire of attachment to close people" N.V. Sabelnikova, D.V. Kashirsky, "Experience of close relationships" K. Brennan and R.K. Fraley, M. Atkinson's Emotional Maturity Scale, "Diagnostics of the Emotional Maturity of the Personality" O.Ya. Chebykina, "Self-evaluation of the generalized type of preference" ("RQ") by K.

Bartholomii and L. Horovyts (adaptation by T.V. Kazantseva), M. Rosenberg's self-esteem scale.

The obtained results are shown in the tables:

Table 1

The results of the correlational analysis of emotional maturity and types of attachment according to the methods "Diagnostics of emotional maturity of the individual" O.Ya. Chebykina and "Self-Assessment of the Generalized Type of Preference" ("RQ") by K. Bartholomii and L. Horovyts (adaptation by T.V. Kazantseva).

	Iek	Eek	IC	EC	Iem	Eem
Type A	–	–	0,349*	–	–	–
Type B	–	–	–	–	–	–
Type C	-0,280*	-0,398**	0,343*	–	-0,331*	–
Type D	–	–	–	–	–	–

Notes: type A – superficial predilection, type B – ambivalent predilection, type C – unique predilection, type D – disorganized predilection, Iek – expression of expressiveness in children, Eek – to convey mood to a partner in spiESlkuvanny, IC – regulation regulation of the behavior of others, Iem – in the mind of understanding the emotions of becoming a lonely middle man, Eem – 2.

Type A ($r=0.019$; $p<0.05$), type B ($r=0.026$; $p<0.05$) and type D ($r=-0.278$; $p<0.05$) are not correlated with one s showing emotional maturity Iek. Type C has a low correlation ($r=-0.280$; $p<0.05$).

Type A ($r=0.081$; $p<0.05$), type B ($r=0.054$; $p<0.05$) and type D ($r=-0.261$; $p<0.05$) do not correlate with Eek, also Type C ($r=0.398$; $p<0.01$) may have a high level of correlation with Eek. Having offended the showcases of expressiveness for this method, they showed a correlation with a unique whimsicality. It is worth mentioning the importance of such special features to transmit your emotions. The demonstration of singing emotional states is not typical for people with a unique whimsicality, but after we take them away there is a correlation link, it is necessary to follow the chain of nutrition in more detail.

Type A ($r=0.349$; $p<0.05$) and type C ($r=0.343$; $p<0.05$) may have a low correlation with IC. It is worth mentioning about the peculiarities of the superior predilection and the unique ability to regulate one's own abilities for the necessary type B ($r=-0.068$; $p<0.05$) and type D ($r=0.019$; $p<0.05$) I can't correlate. Type A ($r=0.004$; $p<0.05$), type B ($r=0.066$; $p<0.05$) and type D ($r=-0.215$; $p<0.05$) do not correlate with Iem, type C ($r=-0.331$; $p<0.05$) may have a low level of negative correlation, which can tell us about the peculiarities of the psyche of a person with a unique type of attachment and burn us about those about whom we are one of the pokaznikiv, the lower type.

No one type of flimsiness according to the method "Self-assessment of a generalized type of similarity" does not have a correlation with the indicator Eem (type A ($r=0.090$; $p<0.05$), type B ($r=-0.109$; $p<0.05$), type C ($r=0.087$; $p<0.05$))

and type D ($r=-0.081$; $p<0.05$)).

Table 2

The results of the correlation analysis of the methods “Self-assessment of a generalized type of likeness” (“RQ”) by K. Barfolomiy and L. Horowitz (adaptation by T.V. Kazantseva) and “An aptitude tester for loved ones” by N.V. Sabelnikova, D.V. Kashirsky.

	U1	A1
Type A	–	–
Type B	–	–
Type C	0,344*	-0,405**
Type D	0,383**	–

Note: type A – superficial predilection, type B – ambivalent predilection, type C – unique predilection, type D – disorganized predilection, U1 – uniqueness, A1 – anxiety about the method of Predilection for loved ones "

According to the results of the analysis of the type of sickness and uniqueness and anxiety, it was revealed: type A (unique: $r=-0.064$; $p<0.05$, anxiety: $r=-0.196$; $p<0.05$) and type B (unique $r=0.062$; $p<0.05$, variable: $r=0.271$; $p<0.05$) does not show the same correlation with indications, also the indicator has a high positive correlation with type C ($r=-0.344$; $p<0.05$,) and D ($r=0.383$; $p<0.01$), and a highly negative correlation with type C anxiety ($r=-0.405$; $p<0.01$).

The peculiarity with a uniquely unorganized pretense can lead to weakness to ignore, unique social situations. For such people, social interaction is an important process, which borrows a lot of resources. Negative correlation gives us the ability to understand why there is one ostentatious person below, and yet another, because of which it is possible to grow visnovkas, why more raven is more unsettled, the lower rhine type shows unique pretentiousness, chi navpaki.

Table 3

The results of the correlation analysis of emotional maturity and types of agreeableness according to the method "Self-assessment of the generalized type of similarity" ("RQ") by K. Bartholomew and L. Horowitz (adaptation by T.V. Kazantseva) and M. Atkinson's Emotional Maturity Scale

Type of attachment	EZ
Type A	-0,398**
Type B	–
Type C	–
Type D	–

Note: type A – superficial predilection, type B – ambivalent predilection, type C – unique predilection, type D – disorganized predilection, EZ – emotional maturity.

Type A (reliable attachment) according to the method "Self-assessment of the generalized type of preference" has a high level of negative correlation ($r=-0.398$; $p<0.01$) with emotional maturity. The results of the indicator of reliable commitment have a negative correlation with the indicator of emotional maturity, this can demonstrate to us that when one of the indicators is at a high level, the other has a low level, thus it can be concluded that reliable commitment is not accompanied by one hundred percent emotional maturity according to the results this technique.

Type B (ambivalent attachment) has no correlation with emotional maturity ($r=0.108$; $p<0.05$), type C (avoidant attachment) has no correlation ($r=-0.266$; $p<0.05$), type D (disorganized attachment) has no correlation ($r=-0.085$; $p<0.05$).

Table 4

The results of the correlation analysis of the methods "Self-assessment of the generalized type of preference" ("RQ") by K. Bartholomii and L. Horovyts (adaptation by T.V. Kazantseva) and "Experience of close relationships" by K. Brennan and R.K. Fraley

Тип прихильності	Y2	C2
Type A	–	–
Type B	–	–
Type C	-0,417**	-0,408**
Type D	0,363*	–

Note: type A – secure attachment, type B – ambivalent attachment, type C – avoidant attachment, type D – disorganized attachment, y2 – avoidance, C2 – anxiety.

Type C commitment ($y2\ r=-0.417$; $p<0.01$). has a high level of negative correlation with the avoidance index, this may indicate that a person with an avoidant type of attachment tends to avoid certain social situations. Also, type C ($b2\ r=-0.408$; $p<0.01$) correlates with anxiety, which may indicate the anxiety of people with this type of attachment, they feel helpless in social situations. Type D ($y2\ r=-0.363$; $p<0.05$) has a slight correlation with the avoidance indicator, this may indicate the tendency of individuals with disorganized attachment to avoid certain circumstances. Type A (avoidance: $r=-0.014$; $p<0.05$, anxiety: $r=-0.157$; $p<0.05$) and type B (avoidance: $r=0.072$; $p<0.05$, anxiety: $r=0.263$; $p<0.05$) have no correlation with any of the indicators.

Table 5

The results of the correlation analysis of the methods "Self-assessment of the generalized type of preference" ("RQ") by K. Bartholomii and L. Horovyts (adaptation by T. V. Kazantseva) and the self-esteem scale by M. Rosenberg.

Type of attachment	Selfrespect
Type A	0,287*
Type B	–
Type C	0,335

Type D	–
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Note: type A – secure attachment, type B – ambivalent attachment, type C – avoidant attachment, type D – disorganized attachment.

Type A ($r=0.287$; $p<0.05$) and type C ($r=0.335$; $p<0.05$) have a low level of positive correlation with the self-esteem indicator. This shows the self-esteem of people with secure attachment and avoidant attachment. Type B ($r=-0.191$; $p<0.05$) and type D ($r=-0.130$; $p<0.05$) have no correlation. A person who has reliable attachment has self-respect, personal boundaries, the ability to defend his opinion and rights. Also, the correlation between avoidance and self-esteem makes it possible to assume strong boundaries of people with this type of attachment, about their stability and self-confidence in personal strengths.

After conducting and analyzing the data obtained during the study, it is possible to draw the following conclusions that emotional maturity has a rather strong relationship with attachment types. According to the results of the empirical study, it was found that a significant number of indicators have a negative correlation, which indicates the interdependence of emotional maturity factors with the type of attachment and their individual psychological characteristics.

Each attachment type was found to correlate differently with avoidance and anxiety scores. Each individual has peculiarities of mental functioning, but the research traces a certain dependence of the perception of social situations and relationships and the type of attachment.